

Additional file 2: Figure S2. *Quantification of S129 phosphorylation of human alpha-synuclein recombinant protein.* An isoelectric focusing gel pH range 5-8 (**A**) was used to separate pS129 from non-phosphorylated h-asyn by loading recombinant h-asyn and pS129 h-asyn protein side by side. In **B**, blots were probed for total h-asyn (syn-1) or pS129 h-asyn (11A5) to determine pS129 h-asyn band. Quantification areas are indicated on total h-asyn blots by dashed boxes. This assay was run independently on three occasions, which yielded estimates of percent phosphorylation of h-asyn at S129 site to be 28.4, 29.5, and 26.0%, respectively, with an average and standard deviation of $28.0 \pm 1.8\%$.